

Synthesis of Dibenzo [b,h] [1,6] Naphthyridine Derivatives : I

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Cyclodehydration of 4-*m*-chloroanilino-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) and the corresponding 8-hydroxy compound (X) in conc. sulphuric acid yielded 4-methoxy-7-hydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine (XIV) and 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine (XV) respectively. The assigned structure was confirmed by an unequivocal cyclodehydration of 8-methoxy-4-(2-carboxy 5-chloro) anilinoquinoline (XVI) to (XIV). Treatment with phosphorus oxychloride converted XIV and XV to the corresponding 7-chloro derivatives respectively (XVII and XVIII).

The objective of the present work was to prepare a suitably substituted quinolinoquinoline, e.g., dibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine¹ (1) as possible antiamebic agents having activity against both the intestinal and extraintestinal forms of the infection in order to see if the presence of both the units of 4-aminoquinoline and halogenated oxyquinoline in the molecule would exhibit any behaviour indicative of synergistic effect. We had also plans to build up a similar prototype of both 8-aminoquinoline and 4-aminoquinoline in the model showing both prophylactic and suppressive antimalarial activity.

(1)

This paper is devoted to the synthesis of several dibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridines which were subsequently² converted to suitable derivatives. Cyclodehydration of suitably substituted 4-anilino-3-carboxyquinolines would afford the desired skeleton¹.

Recent work in this laboratory has established a novel way of synthesising 4-anilinoquinolines in high yield³ involving polyphosphoric acid induced cyclodehydration of β -anilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacryloanilides and the related α -cyanoderivatives. It was significant that in the above reaction with ethoxycarbonyl derivative, simultaneous hydrolysis and

1. W. O. Kermack and (Mrs.) Nora E. Storey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1389.
2. A. K. Sen and Prabal Sengupta (communicated).
3. A. K. Sen and K. Mitra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 851.

decarboxylation took place during cyclodehydration, whereas in the case of the corresponding α -cyano derivative, concomitant conversion of the cyano group to carboxamide occurred. In our attempts, similar reaction of β -*o*-methoxy (and ethoxy) anilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide with polyphosphoric acid, the unchanged product was recovered when the reaction was carried out at 100°. Extensive decomposition occurred when the reaction was carried out above 125°, from which no pure product could be isolated. Cyclodehydration of β -*o*-methoxyanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (II) to ethyl 4-*m*-chloroanilino-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (III) was however achieved with phosphorous oxychloride in rather low yield. Attempted cyclodehydration of β -(*p*-methoxy *o*-nitro) anilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide with polyphosphoric acid, phosphorus oxychloride or polyphosphoric ester⁴ has led to the recovery of the starting material.

The general method of preparation of 4-anilinoquinolines involves the conversion of 4-hydroxyquinoline to the 4-chloroderivative and subsequent condensation with anilines thereof⁵. The reaction of anilines with ethoxymethylenemalonate (EMME) affords α -carbethoxy- β -anilinoacrylate which on ring closure in boiling diphenyl oxide yields 4-hydroxy-3-carbethoxyquinolines⁵. Levai and his coworkers⁶ have evolved an elegant method of preparation of ethyl α -carbethoxy- β -*m*-chloroanilinoacrylate using *m*-chloroaniline, diethylmalonate and ethylorthoformate. Using a slight modification of the procedure, *N*:*N'*-bis(*o*-methoxyphenyl) formamidine and excess of ethylorthoformate was similarly reacted with diethylmalonate to ethyl α -carbethoxy- β -*o*-methoxyanilinoacrylate in 80% yield. The ring closure was effected in the usual way to ethyl 4-hydroxy-8-methoxy-

4. (a) Takeshi Amakasu and Kikmasa Sato, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 1435.

(b) Kanaoka, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 2591.

5. R. C. Elderfield in *Heterocyclic Compounds*. Vol. 4, John Wiley and Sons, New York, Chapter I.

6. L. Levai, C. Ritvay-Emandity and G. Csepregy, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 4003.

quinoline-3-carboxylate (VII). The hydroxy compound was converted to the 4-chloro derivative (VIII) with a mixture of phosphorus pentachloride and phosphorus oxychloride. The latter on condensation with *m*-chloroaniline yielded ethyl 4-*m*-chloroanilino-8-methoxy quinoline-3-carboxylate (III) and was found to be identical with the sample prepared by direct cyclodehydration of β -*o*-methoxyanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (II) with phosphorus oxychloride (*vide supra*).

The ethyl ester (III) was saponified with alcoholic potassium hydroxide to 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX). Treatment of this ester (III) with hydrobromic acid effected simultaneous demethylation of the 8-methoxy group to give 8-hydroxy 4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X). The carboxyquinoline derivatives (IX and X) were decarboxylated to the related 4-*m*-chloroanilino quinolines (XI and XII) and were found to be identical with the compounds made from 4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (XIII).

Cyclodehydration of 4-*m*-chloroanilino-8-methoxy (and hydroxy) quinoline-3-carboxylic acids (IX and X) to the desired tetracyclic system was effected with conc. sulfuric acid to afford 4-methoxy-7-hydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h] [1,6] naphthyridine (XIV) and the corresponding 4-hydroxy compound (XV) respectively. We were cognizant of the fact that the ring closure involving *m*-substituted aniline might occur to give two possible isomers. It is, however, known that several cyclisation reactions involving *m*-substituted anilines, proceed to a remarkable degree in one direction involving the position *para* to the *meta* substituent present in the aniline molecule³. In this case also we were able to isolate only one product. Cyclodehydration of 8-methoxy-4-(2-carboxy-5-chloro)anilinoquinoline (XVI), would, however, offer an unambiguous synthesis. Controversy exists in similar cyclodehydration of N-4'-pyridylanthranilic acid and its benzoderivatives. The chemical properties of the resulting products obtained in a number of laboratories appeared to indicate their formulation to anthranil⁷⁻¹⁰. In the present work 8-methoxy-4-(2-carboxy-5-chloro) anilino quinoline (XVI), formed by the condensation of 8-methoxy-4-chloroquinoline (XIII) with 4-chloroanthranilic acid, on similar cyclodehydration with conc. sulfuric acid gave the product which is found to be identical with the product obtained by cyclodehydration of 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX). This unequivocally establishes the feasibility of Fridel Craft type acylation reaction to effect similar ring closures. Constant boiling hydrobromic acid converted 4-methoxy-7-hydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h] [1,6] naphthyridine (XIV) to the corresponding 4-hydroxy compound (XV).

Cyclodehydration reaction involving conc. sulfuric acid always resulted in significant amount of insoluble high melting material. Cyclodehydration of 8-methoxy (and hydroxy)-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acids (IX and X) with phosphorus oxychloride and subsequent addition of the reaction product to ice water containing alkali, gave 4-methoxy (and hydroxy)-7,10-dichlorodibenzo [b,h] [1,6] naphthyridine (XVII and XVIII) along with

7. C. C. Price and R. M. Roberts, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1946, **11**, 463.
8. W. O. Kermack and A. P. Weatherhead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 726.
9. V. Petrow, *ibid.*, 1945, 927.
10. V. Petrow and B. Sturgeon, *ibid.*, 1949, 1157.

small quantities of 7-hydroxy derivatives (XIV and XV). Direct addition of the reaction product to ice-water however gave the 7-hydroxy compounds (XIV and XV) in an yield,

significantly higher, compared to sulfuric acid induced cyclodehydration reaction. Treatment of 4-methoxy (and hydroxy)-7-hydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridines (XIV and XV) with phosphorus oxychloride also effected smooth conversion to their 7-chloro analogues (XVII and XVIII). These 7-chloro compounds resemble 5-chloroacridines; in particular they are stable to alkali but readily revert back to the 7-hydroxy derivatives in presence of acid. Similar observations regarding the acid labile nature of 7-chloro compounds have also been recorded by Kermack¹. 7-Hydroxydibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridines (XIV and XV) are yellowish in colour but become white when moistened with water or ethanol. They exhibit intense greenish yellow fluorescence in ethanol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethoxycarbonylaceto-m-chloroanilide (I): Malon di-*m*-chloroanilide was prepared by heating a mixture of *m*-chloroaniline (2 moles) and diethylmalonate (1 mole) at 160° for two hours, evolved ethanol being allowed to escape and the product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 173°. ¹¹ A mixture of the dianilide (22 g., 0.068 mole) and diethylmalonate (75 g., 0.47 mole) was stirred and kept at 155–160° for 2½ hr. Excess of diethylmalonate was distilled under reduced pressure and the residual mass was warmed with benzene. On cooling, the dianilide (5 g, 0.0154 mole) separated out and removed. Removal of benzene from the mother liquor left a viscous residue (26 g., 0.108 mole), presumed to be ethoxycarbonylaceto-*m*-chloroanilide, was rather a low melting solid which could not be characterised and was directly proceeded with the next step.

11. A. K. Sen and Prabal Sengupta *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 857.

*β -o-Methoxyanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (II)*: A mixture of ethoxycarbonylaceto-*m*-chloroanilide (30.1 g., 0.125 mole), ethylorthoformate (18.5 g, 0.125 mole) and *o*-anisidine (15.38 g, 0.125 mole) was heated under reflux at 110–115°, till the distillation of ethanol ceased. The residue was washed with ethanol and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 142–143°, yield 39 g (83%). (Found : C, 61.30; H, 5.10; C₁₉H₁₉O₄N₂Cl requires, C, 60.88; H, 5.07%).

*Ethyl 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylate (III)*: (a) A mixture of *β -o*-methoxyanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (75 g, 0.2 mole), phosphorus oxychloride (60.60 g, 0.4 mole) and pure and dry toluene (500 ml) was heated under reflux for 16 hr. The semisolid mass, obtained on removal of toluene and excess phosphorus oxychloride under reduced pressure, was dissolved in ethanol (120 ml), cooled and the solution made turbid with ether. Chilling for two days gave crystalline material which was collected, washed with alcohol-ether mixture and dried. This was dissolved in water (400 ml) (charcoal) and basified with a slight excess of aqueous ammonia. The solid (18.0 g, 25%) was collected, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145–146°.

(b) A mixture of ethyl 8-methoxy-4-chloroquinoline-3-carboxylate (VIII) (3.5 g, 0.015 mole) and *m*-chloroaniline (1.905 g, 0.015 mole) was heated under reflux in chloroform (10 ml) for one hour. The gummy residue, obtained after removing the solvent under reduced pressure, was dissolved in water (30 ml) (charcoal) and basified with a slight excess of ammonia. The product was collected and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145–146°; yield, 5.0 g, (93.5%). Mixed melting point determination of the samples prepared as in (a) and (b) showed no depression. Their infrared spectra were superimposable. (Found : C, 64.32; H, 5.2; C₁₉H₁₇O₃N₂Cl requires, C, 64.00; H, 4.77%).

*β -o-Methoxyanilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (IV)*: An equimolecular mixture of cyanoaceto-*m*-chloroanilide, *o*-anisidine and ethylorthoformate was heated in an oil bath at 120–125° for 45 min. when the distillation of ethanol almost ceased. The residual solid was washed with ethanol and crystallised from acetic acid, yield 92%, m.p. 195°. (Found : C, 62.91; H, 4.45; C₁₇H₁₄O₂N₃Cl requires, C, 62.30; H, 4.25%).

*β -o-Ethoxyanilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (V)*: This was prepared essentially as described above (IV) from *o*-phenitidine (9.59 g; 0.07 mole), cyanoaceto-*m*-chloroanilide (13.62 g, 0.07 mole) and ethylorthoformate (10.36 g; 0.27 mole) and crystallised from ethanol; yield, 22.0 g (92.5%), m.p. 142–143°. (Found : C, 63.24; H, 5.11; C₁₈H₁₆O₂N₃Cl requires : C, 63.25; H, 4.7%).

Ethyl 4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (VII): A mixture of N:N'-bis-(2-methoxyphenyl) formamidine¹² (61.45 g; 0.24 mole) and ethylorthoformate (46.62 g; 0.24 mole + 20% excess) was maintained at 135–140° while diethylmalonate (75.8 g; 0.48 mole) was added during 12 hr with efficient stirring. After the addition was completed, the heating and stirring was continued for a further period of three hours. Excess of components were removed under reduced pressure and the residual oil was added dropwise during one hour to vigorously boiling diphenyl oxide (250 ml). Heating was continued for 45 min.

longer. After keeping for 3 days the solid was collected and recrystallised from cyclohexanone (45.4 g) m.p. 234–236°. Mixed melting point determination with a sample prepared according to Lauer, *et al.*¹³, recorded no depression.

Ethyl 4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (VIII): Ethyl 4-hydroxy 8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (9.88 g; 0.04 mole) was added to a cooled mixture of phosphorus oxychloride (12.6 ml) and phosphorus pentachloride (8.2 g) and heated under reflux for two hours at 110–120°. The mixture was cooled and added to crushed ice containing alkali and chloroform (40 ml), care being taken so that the temperature did not rise above 10°. The organic layer was separated, washed with cold water (10 ml) and dried (Na_2SO_4). Chloroform was removed and the residue extracted with petroleum ether (40–60°) (50 ml), concentrated to half and chilled. The solid (7.25 g, 68%) was collected and recrystallised from petroleum ether (40–60°) m.p. 75–76°. (Found: C, 59.1; H, 4.8; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires: C, 58.76; H, 4.43%).

8-Methoxy-4-m-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX): A solution of ethyl 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylate (14.26 g; 0.04 mole) in ethanolic KOH (150 ml, 20%) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. The potassium salt which soon began to precipitate out, was collected and dissolved in water. The solution on neutralisation with hydrochloric acid (congo red) gave the desired compound. The acid is not soluble in ordinary solvents. An analytical sample was prepared by dissolving the solid in aqueous alkali and reprecipitating with acid, m.p. 271–272° (decomp.), yield 12.5 g (95.8%). (Found: C, 62.46; H, 4.24; $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 62.19; H, 3.97%).

4-m-Chloroanilino-8-methoxyquinoline (XI): (a) 8-Methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline 3-carboxylic acid (1.0 g) was slowly heated above its melting point (270–280°) for 10 min. when the solid melted with effervescence. The residue was extracted with boiling ethanol, charcoaled, filtered and cooled. The compound (0.50 g) on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 252–253°. Mixed melting point determination with a sample prepared as in (b) recorded no depression.

(b) A mixture of *m*-chloroaniline (0.50 g; 0.004 mole) and 4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (0.772 g; 0.004 mole) in dil. hydrochloric acid (aq.) (10 ml) was heated for 3 hr on a steam bath. The separated solid was collected, triturated with aqueous ammonia, filtered, washed with water and dried; yield, 1.10 g (97%). On crystallisation from ethanol, the compound melted at 252–253°. (Found: C, 67.22; H, 5.08; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{OCl}$ requires C, 67.48; H, 4.53%).

4-Hydroxy-3-carboxy-8-methoxyquinoline: Ethyl 4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylate was hydrolysed essentially as described¹³.

4-Chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (XIII): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (23 g) and diphenyl oxide (160 ml) was boiled for 90 min. cooled, and phosphorus oxychloride was added. The temperature of the mixture was then slowly raised to 135–140° and maintained there at that temperature with stirring for 1 hr. The thoroughly cooled mixture was cautiously treated with aq. hydrochloric acid (10%; 100 ml.) and left in the refrigerator. Diphenyl oxide crystallised out. The aqueous portion was washed with

ether (2 × 25 ml) and basified with a slight excess of aq. NaOH (10%). The solid (16.5 g; 77.7%) was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-water, m.p. 78–79°. The reported¹³ melting point is 79–80°.)

8-Hydroxy-4-m-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X): A mixture of ethyl 4-*m*-chloroanilino-8-methoxyquinoline-3-carboxylate (10.68 g; 0.03 mole) and hydrobromic acid (40 ml) was heated under gentle reflux. After two hours the crystalline hydrobromide began to separate. Heating was continued for 4 hr longer and cooled. The solid was collected, washed with water. It was purified by dissolving in aq. potassium hydroxide (5%, 150 ml) and reprecipitated with dil. hydrochloric acid (congo red). Yield, 8.9 g; 87%, m.p. 268–270° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.07; H, 3.65; C₁₆H₁₁O₃N₂Cl requires C, 61.05; H, 3.49%.)

8-Hydroxy-4-m-chloroanilinoquinoline (XII): (a) 8-Hydroxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (0.314 g; 0.003 mole) was heated at 270–275° for 15 min. when the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased. The solid left was extracted with ethanol (charcoal), filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and diluted with water. The desired compound (0.20 g, 70.2%) was crystallised twice from ethanol-water, m.p. 146–147°. The yellow solid turned brick red when dried on steam bath. (Found: C, 66.95; H, 4.28; C₁₅H₁₁N₂OCl requires C, 66.54; H, 4.07%.)

(b) A mixture of 4-*m*-chloroanilino-8-methoxyquinoline (XIII) (1.37 g; 0.005 mole) and hydrobromic acid (15 ml) was heated under gentle reflux for 4 hr. Hydrobromic acid was removed under reduced pressure and the product was triturated with aq. ammonia. The solid (1.15 g, 85%) was collected and recrystallised from ethanol-water, m.p. 146–147°, mixed m.p. determination with a sample prepared as in (a) recorded no depression.

8-Methoxy-4-(2-carboxy-5-chloro)anilinoquinoline (XVI): A solution of 4-chloro-8-methoxyquinoline (4.60 g; 0.025 mole) and 4-chloroanthranilic acid¹⁴ (4.25 g; 0.025 mole) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. The cooled solution was then added to crushed ice. The solid (6.80 g; 82.8%) was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 261–262° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.42; H, 4.20 Calc. for C₁₇H₁₃O₃N₂Cl: C, 62.19; H, 3.97%.)

4-Methoxy-7-hydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine (XIV): (a) To ice cooled conc. sulphuric acid (15 ml), 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) (1.64 g; 0.005 mole) was added and warmed on a steam bath for 1 hr, when the colour slowly deepened to dark red. The mixture was cooled, added to crushed ice, filtered and washed with water. The solid was warmed with sodium hydroxide (1%, 200 ml), filtered to remove insoluble impurity if any. Neutralisation of the alkaline solution to pH 7.5 gave the desired compound (0.38 g.). Several recrystallisations from ethanol raised the melting point to 280–282°. λ_{max}^{EtOH} 269m μ (ϵ 42500), 315 (15200), 365 (8950). (Found: C, 66.05; H, 3.89; Calc. for C₁₇H₁₁O₂N₂Cl: C, 65.76; H, 3.54%.)

(b) The deep red solution formed by the addition of 8-methoxy 4-(2-carboxy 5-chloro)-anilinoquinoline (XVI) (0.82 g; 0.0025 mole) to cooled conc. sulfuric acid (7.5 ml), was heated on steam bath for 1 hr. The cooled mixture was added slowly with stirring to crushed ice. The solid material (0.15 g) was collected and worked up as in (a), m.p. 280–282°.

14. D. Kunovi, *C.A.*, 1962, 56, 3442.

(c) Phosphorus oxychloride (8 ml) was slowly added to 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, (0.82 g, 0.0025 mole) kept at 0–5°. The mixture was then heated under reflux for 4 hr at 115–120°. The yellow mass, left after removal of phosphorus oxychloride under reduced pressure, was poured into ice water, allowed to attain the room temperature and kept there for 1 hr. The solid (0.55 g) was collected and worked up as in (a), m.p. 280–282°. Mixed melting point determinations of the samples prepared as in (a), (b) and (c) showed no depression.

4-Methoxy-7,10-dichlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6]naphthyridine (XVII): Phosphorus oxychloride was slowly added to 8-methoxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (1 g) kept at 0–5°. The clear solution was heated under reflux at 115–120° for 4 hr. The cooled solution was poured into ice containing adequate sodium hydroxide and the solid was collected. The dry mass was extracted with boiling dry toluene (30 ml) over a pellet of potassium hydroxide and filtered hot. On removal of the solvent, the filtrate left the title compound (0.25 g) which when crystallised several times from toluene melted at 215–218°. (Found: C, 62.17; H, 3.35; Cl, 22.02. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₀Cl₂N₂O: C, 62.06; H, 3.04; Cl, 21.58%).

4,7-Dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6]naphthyridine (XV): (a) Cyclodehydration of 8-hydroxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X) (6.3 g; 0.002 mole) with phosphorus oxychloride (12 ml) was carried out as described earlier in the preparation of XIV (b). The reaction product was poured into ice-water, allowed to attain the room temperature, kept there for 1 hr, basified with a slight excess of ammonia; the solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 295–300°, yield 4.4 g (74%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 270 m μ (ϵ 33000), 315 (18500), 368 (7700) (Found: C, 65.15; H, 3.40; Calc. for C₁₆H₉O₂N₂Cl: C, 64.75; H, 3.04%).

(b) 8-Hydroxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X) (3.14 g; 0.01 mole) was treated with conc. sulfuric acid essentially as described in XIV (a). The reaction product was worked up as above (a); yield 0.68 g, m.p. 295–300°.

(c) A mixture of 4-methoxy-7-hydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine (1.2 g, 0.004 mole) and hydrobromic acid (25 ml) was heated under reflux. After 2 hr crystals began to separate. Heating was continued for 1 hr more. The solid obtained was triturated with ammonia and worked up as in (a), yield 0.8 g, m.p. 295–300°. Mixed m.p. determination of the samples prepared as in (a), (b) and (c) showed no depression.

4-Hydroxy-6,10-dichlorodibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine (XVIII): (a) This was prepared essentially as described for the preparation of (XVII) from 8-hydroxy-4-*m*-chloroanilinoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X) (6.3 g, 0.02 mole) and phosphorus oxychloride. The compound was crystallised from dry toluene; yield 2.7 g (43%), m.p. 202–203°. (Found: C, 61.10; H, 2.85; Cl, 22.05; Calc. for C₁₆H₈N₂Cl₂O: C, 60.95; H, 2.54; Cl, 22.53%).

(b) The procedure adopted in the case (XVII) was employed using 4,7-dihydroxydibenzo [b,h][1,6] naphthyridine (XV) (1.5 g; 0.005 mole) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 ml). The solid was crystallised from dry toluene; yield 0.40 g (25%), m.p. 202–203°. Mixed m.p. determination of the samples prepared as in (a) and (b) showed no depression.

The initial deep red colour, formed by addition of 5% aq. hydrochloric acid to the 7-chloro compound (XVIII), slowly changed to greenish yellow with fluorescence and a white

solid began to form. The mixture was then heated on steam bath for 15 mins, cooled and basified with ammonia in slight excess. The solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol and found to be identical with the corresponding 7-hydroxy derivative (XV).

β-(*p*-Methoxy-*o*-nitro) anilino-*α*-cyanoacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (VI) : This was prepared essentially as in the preparation of (V) from cyanoaceto-*m*-chloroanilide, orthoformic ester and 2-nitro-4-methoxyaniline and crystallised from glacial acetic acid; yield 85%, m.p. 202°. (Found : C, 54.90; H, 3.62; Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃N₄O₄Cl : C, 54.75; H, 3.49%).

Attempted cyclodehydration of (VI) with polyphosphoric ester.⁴ : *β*-(*p*-Methoxy-*o*-nitro)-anilino-*α*-cyanoacrylo-*m*-chloroanilide (VI) (3.725 g, 0.01 mole) was added to ice-cooled polyphosphoric ester [prepared by heating on a steam bath a mixture of phosphorus pentoxide (5.52 g) and dry ethanol (5.6 ml) until a clear solution was obtained] and heated for 4 hrs at 125–130° when the mixture became homogeneous. The cooled mixture was added to ice, basified with a slight excess of ammonia and the solid (3.0 g) collected. Treatment of the product with hot acetic acid gave 1.9 g of starting material and left a high melting resinous mass.

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